

THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SILICIC ACID
SOLS. PART III. VARIATIONS IN THE p_H , SPECIFIC
CONDUCTIVITY AND TOTAL ACIDITY OF
SILICIC ACID SOLS WITH DILUTION
AND WITH TEMPERATURE.*

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The free and total acidities of silicic acid sols change linearly with concentration and the degree of dissociation remains practically constant. The variation of conductivity with dilution shows departures from a linear relation. The values of the hydrogen ion concentration of the sol and its dilutions calculated from the p_H and the specific conductivity show fair agreement. The free and total acids of silicic acid sols as also their degree of dissociation do not materially change with temperature between 1° and 50°. The specific conductivity increases linearly with temperature. The temperature coefficient at 18° is about 2%.

The potentiometric titration curves of silicic acid sols with concentrated alkalis resemble those of a weak monobasic acid in true solution (Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 589.) On the gradual addition of alkali the p_H rapidly rises to about 9.5, then at a slower rate and the curve finally shows an inflexion point (second inflexion point) between p_H 11.0 and 11.7 corresponding to the formation of NaHSiO_3 . The first dissociation constant of silicic acid has been obtained from the values of S , the concentration of dissolved silica and the following relation

$$K_1 S = [H^+] \{ [H^+] + [B^+] - [OH^-] \},$$

where K_1 is the first dissociation constant of silicic acid; B^+ , the concentration of Na^+ . K_1 has a mean value of 5.2×10^{-10} . On closer examination, however, the resemblance with a weak acid in true solution appears to be superficial. The buffer capacity ($\Delta B / \Delta p_H$) of the sol is considerably greater than that of a dissolved acid having the same dissociation constant and total acidity as the sol. Titration curves with dilute solution (0.01N) of NaOH , Ba(OH)_2 and Ca(OH)_2 show an inflexion point in the acid region between p_H 4.5 and 5.6. The range of p_H in which the inflexion point has been observed with several bases are with NaOH , 5.17 to 5.4; with Ba(OH)_2 , 4.80 to 5.6; and with Ca(OH)_2 ,

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4.5 to 5.5. The total acid at this inflexion point and the free acid calculated from the initial p_H of the sol are of the order of $10^{-4}N$; the degree of dissociation, i.e., the ratio of free to total acids has been found to lie between 0.5 to 1.0. The total acid neutralised at the first inflexion point is the same for all these bases. The slopes of the titration curves, however, show that the relative intensities with which different bases react with the sol are in the order $Ca(OH)_2 > Ba(OH)_2 > NaOH$. The amount of acid neutralised at the inflexion point in the titration curve with a dilute base, however, does not represent the total neutralisable acid of the sol. Much larger amounts of acids are set free by repeatedly leaching the sol with solutions of neutral salts (Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939 16, 607). But the total acid thus found constitutes a very small fraction (about 0.0013) of the amount of silicon dioxide (estimated as orthosilicic acid) present, indicating that the reaction is confined to the surface. The amount of acid liberated by different chlorides are in the order: $Ba^{++} > Ca^{++} > Na^+ > Li^+$. In the present investigation the variations with (i) dilution and (ii) temperature have been studied. Experimental details and fuller references to previous work have been given in the two papers referred to above.

Change brought about on Dilution.

Rabinowitsch and Laskin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 104, 390) studied the variations of free and total acids with dilution. They concluded that the degree of dissociation increased with dilution reaching the apparently improbable value of 330 per cent at a dilution of 128. They attributed this increase to the progressive hydrolysis of the acid anhydride molecule contained in the colloidal particles and their subsequent dissociation. The total amount of neutralisable hydrogen ions estimated by multiplying the total acidity of the diluted sols by the dilution greatly exceeds the total amount of neutralisable acid of the undiluted sol. In a later paper Rabinowitsch and Kargin (*Trans Faraday. Soc.*, 1935, 31, 289), however, attributed the hydrogen ion activities of silicic acid sols measured by Rabinowitsch and Laskin (*loc. cit.*) and others to foreign electrolytes. In previous work in this laboratory (Mukherjee and co-workers, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1934, 4, 733; Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 67, 178) on the changes in the free and total acid of silicic acid sols with dilution, it was observed that the hydrogen ion activities of the sol varied with dilution in a manner different from that of an acid in true solution. The sols used by Mukherjee and co-workers contained appreciable amounts of hydrochloric acid and some of them also contained small but visible flocks. The titration curves were often irregular and showed several breaks simulating those of a polybasic

acid. These breaks were traced to the presence of these flocks and non-attainment of equilibrium and in later work in this laboratory (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*) the improvements in the experimental technique have resulted in reproducible and smooth titration curves. The present investigation has been carried out with more carefully purified sols.

Variations in the p_H and Specific Conductivity on Dilution.

The variations with dilutions in the p_H , free acidity and specific conductivity of sols U and W are shown in Table I. Water having a specific conductivity of 1.1 to 1.15×10^{-6} mho at 35° has been used for diluting the sols.

TABLE I.

System.	Colloid content g. mol. per litre.	p_H .	Specific conductivity $\times 10^6$ mho.			Free acidity $\times 10^6 N$ $\times$ dilution.	Corrected sp. condy. $\times 10^6$ mho. $\times$ dilution.
			sol.	ultrafiltrate.	corrected†		
Sol U	0.30	4.38 4.37	46.3	27.2	19.1	4.20	19.1
" U/2	0.15	4.54 4.68 4.67	23.5	16.2	7.3	4.60	14.6
" U/4	0.075	4.96 4.95	10.3	6.3	4.0	4.44	16.0
" U/8	0.038	5.29 5.20	7.1	5.1	2.0	4.48	16.0
Sol W	0.26	3.87 3.85 3.86	76.5	9.5	67.0	13.8	67.0
" W/2	0.13	4.13	35.9	5.2	30.7	14.8	61.4
" W/4	0.065	4.52	16.5	3.0	13.5	12.0	54.0

* Specific conductivity of equilibrium water is calculated to be about 1.0×10^{-6} mho at this temperature.

† The specific conductivity of a sol minus that of its ultrafiltrate.

Considering the experimental errors and methods of calculation, it may be concluded from the data given in Table I that the concentration of neutralisable hydrogen ion obtained by multiplying the hydrogen ion concentration of the dilute sol by the number of times the sol has been diluted remains practically constant. The conductivity obtained by mul-

tipling the corrected specific conductivity with the dilution show variations somewhat greater than the experimental error.

Agreement between Activity and Conductivity Data.

The hydrogen ion concentrations have been calculated from their corrected specific conductivity (Table I) using the formula,

$$C_H = \frac{1000 \times \text{corrected specific conductivity}}{U_H + V_{\text{colloid}}}$$

where $U_H = 404$ and $V_{\text{colloid}} = 24$ at 35° , compared in Table II with those from the p_H values. The above value of V_{colloid} has been calculated from c.v. measurements which show that it has a value of 20 at 25° and temperature coefficient of 2 %.

TABLE II.

System.	p_H .	Corrected* sp. condy. $\times 10^6$.	Free acidity $\times 10^4 N$ calculated from p_H .	Corr. sp. condy.
Sol U	4.38	19.1 mho	4.20	4.47
„ U/2	4.63	7.3	2.30	1.71
„ U/4	4.96	4.0	1.11	0.93
„ U/8	5.25	2.0	0.56	0.47
Sol W	3.86	67.0	13.8	15.7
„ W/2	4.13	30.7	7.4	7.2
„ W/4	4.52	13.5	3.0	3.2

The agreement should be considered fair in view of the experimental errors and the methods of calculation. Pauli and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, **36**, 325; 1926, **38**, 289; 1937, **79**, 67) obtained that the C_H calculated from specific conductivity was higher than those from the p_H . It is probable that account was not taken of the foreign electrolytes present in the sol.

Variations in the Total Acidity and Degree of Dissociation with Dilution.

The total acidity of sol W and its dilution as also of sol U obtained, by titration with NaOH, are given in Table III and the degree of dissociation

* Taken from Table I.

† Calculated at the first inflexion point in the titration curve with NaOH.

calculated from the free acid given in Table II, have also been shown in the same table.

TABLE III.

System.	p_H .	Free acid $\times 10^3 N$ from p_H .	Total acid $\times 10^3 N$.	Degree of dissociation. (%)
Sol U	4.38	4.20	4.0	105 (completely dissociated)
Sol W	3.86	13.8	17.8(4.85)**	77.5
„ W/2	4.23	7.4	9.6(4.93)**	77.0
„ W/4	4.52	3.0	4.1(5.37)**	74.0

** Figures within brackets give the p_H at inflexion.

The total acidity of sol W changes almost linearly with concentration within the limits of experimental errors. The degree of dissociation about 77.5%, does not materially change on dilution. For the same ratio of dilution Rabinowitsch and Laskin (*loc. cit.*) observed a change from 80% to 90%.

A comparison of the free to total acidity shows that sol U is completely and sol W only 77.5% dissociated. This difference cannot, however, be ascribed only to the difference in the p_H of the two sols.

Assuming colloidal silicic acid to behave as a uni-36 valent electrolyte in true solution, calculations using the equation as developed by Onsager (*Physikal. Z.*, 1926, 27, 388) give a value of 0.774 for its degree of dissociation at a concentration of 17.8N. The variations with dilution in the degree of dissociation of such an electrolyte have been calculated and shown in Table IV.

$$\Lambda_0 - \Lambda = \frac{29.0(Z_+ + Z_-)}{(DT)^{0.5\eta}} + \frac{0.986 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{1.5}} W \Lambda_0 \sqrt{2\mu} \quad \dots (i)$$

where
$$W = Z_+ Z_- \frac{2q}{\sqrt{x+q}}$$

and
$$q = \frac{Z_+ Z_- (U_1 + U_2)}{(Z_+ + Z_-)(Z_- U_1 + Z_+ U_2)}$$

TABLE IV.

Conc. (N)	...	...	0.000178	0.000029	0.000045
Degree of dissn. (%)	...	...	77.4	83.9	89.9

The degree of dissociation of the hypothetical uni-36 valent electrolyte increases regularly with dilution, whereas that of sol W (Table II) remains practically constant. The variations in the degree of dissociation of colloidal silica are thus not in accordance with Onsager's theory.

*Changes with Temperature.**

The free and total acids of three silicic acid sols T, U and W and the specific conductivity of sols T and W at several temperatures are shown in Table V.

TABLE V.

Sol.	Specific conductivity $\times 10^6$ mho.					p_a			Free acid $\times 10^6 N$			Total acid $\times 10^6 N$			%				
	1°	4°	30°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°		
T	31.3	51.0	57.0	69.8		4.15	4.19		7.3	7.1		10.5	10.0		69.5	71.0			
						4.12	4.11												
U						4.34	4.38	4.41	4.3	4.2	4.0	4.0	4.2	4.0	completely dissociated				
						4.39	4.39												
W	33.0					76.5	96.0	3.86	3.85	3.85	13.8	13.8	14.1	17.4	17.8	18.2	79	77.5	77
						3.86	3.86												

It will be seen that a variation of temperature from 1° to 50° produces practically no change in the free and total acids. The amount of acid

FIG. 1.

* A note on this subject has been published in (this JOURNAL), 1941, 16, 263.

neutralised at the inflexion point thus appears to be a fixed quantity. It has also been observed (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*) that the total acid neutralised at the first inflexion point in the titration curves* with different bases is practically the same. The inflexion point acquires a special significance in this sense. The potentiometric titration curves of sols T and U (Fig. 1) at different temperatures practically coincide with one another. Those of sol W (Fig. 2) though giving almost the same total acidity at the inflexion points show a somewhat stronger buffer action with an increase in temperature.

The specific conductivity changes linearly with temperature (Fig. 3). The temperature coefficient at 18° is 1.93 % in the case of sol T and 2.3 % with sol W. Pauli and Palmrich (*loc. cit.*) obtained similar linear variations between 0° and 90° and a temperature coefficient of about 2% at 18°.

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to titrations at 1°, 35° and 50°

FIG. 3.

Curves 1 and 2 refer respectively to sol W and sol T.

It appears from the data cited in Table V that the degree of dissociation of silicic acid sols do not change materially with temperature between 1° and 50°. The change in the degree of dissociation of an electrolyte having

* Titration curves of only sol U are given in Fig. 1.

the same concentration as sol W and 36-valent anion (p. 21) have been calculated using Onsager's equation (*loc. cit.*) and shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Temperature	... 1°	35°	50°
Degree of dissn. (%)	... 82.7	77.4	76.3

The calculated degree of dissociation is found to decrease with temperature. The effect of temperature on the degree of dissociation of silicic acid sols cannot, therefore, be explained from a consideration of Onsager's theory.

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